

1 Supplement: Large-scale impacts of the 2023 Canadian wildfires on the Northern
2 Hemisphere atmosphere

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5 Fig. 1-S. Model temperature difference (FIRE – noFIRE) average and variance of the global
6 domain, NH, and Canada, as a function of ensemble members.

7 As discussed in the manuscript, Fig. 1-S contains the model temperature difference (FIRE
8 – noFIRE) average and variance across the global domain, NH, and Canada, as a function of
9 ensemble members. As the number of members increases the signal of average differences
10 stabilizes, which means that the number of members should be sufficient to overcome model
11 uncertainties. The following set of figures and their discussion supplements the manuscript
12 discussion of the model AOD and measurement AOD comparison.

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14 Fig. 2-S: Bias of monthly model AOD when compared to MODIS AOD for the FIRE simulation
 15 (left), and the noFIRE simulation (right). The panels (a,c,e,g,i) and (b,d,f,h,j) represent the data for
 16 the months May-September.

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To further validate the modelling of the wildfire emissions, a comparison with MODIS AOD data and FIRE AOD along with noFIRE AOD has been performed (Fig. 2-S). The methodology for this comparison is as follows: monthly MODIS AOD data is compared with the monthly output model AOD data which has, after being regridded to the resolution of the MODIS AOD data, had the points lacking in data of the MODIS AOD data set applied to it as a mask. The FIRE AOD and noFIRE AOD data has also been normalized in the same manner as the MODIS AOD data, which is to their highest respective value. The method consists of flattening the AOD maps to 1-dimensional arrays, then computing the Pearson correlation coefficient between them.

25 Both the MODIS data set and the FIRE and noFIRE datasets are normalized to their highest
26 respective values, with the highest value in the normalized sets being 1.

27 The Pearson correlation indices computed from the 1D correlation analysis between the
28 FIRE AOD and MODIS AOD are as follows: from May to September, 0.302, 0.433, 0.454, 0.275,
29 0.29, with an average of 0.351. The average difference between the FIRE AOD and MODIS AOD
30 are as follows: from May to September, 0.141, 0.13, 0.21, 0.185, 0.091, with an average of 0.151.
31 Meanwhile, the Pearson correlation indices computed from the 1D correlation analysis between
32 the noFIRE AOD and MODIS AOD are as follows: from May to September, 0.006, 0.166, 0.061,
33 0.091, 0.124, with an average of 0.089. The average difference between the noFIRE AOD and
34 MODIS AOD are as follows: from May to September, 0.166, 0.207, 0.292, 0.243, 0.166, with an
35 average of 0.214. The FIRE/noFIRE correlation ratio is 3.943, while the noFIRE/FIRE difference
36 ratio is 1.417. The results are similar to the AERONET AOD comparison.

37 Regarding systematic AOD underestimation compared with MODIS data, there will
38 always exist various discrepancies between reality and modelled scenario, and the AOD
39 difference is systematically lower because these discrepancies can add up to a slightly higher real
40 AOD. For example, the EC-Earth3 configuration that we have implemented in our study, as
41 described in the paper, does not have a “fire model component”. As such, the GFAS emissions
42 are inserted into the model directly, and any potential pyroconvective effects are neglected. These
43 pyroconvective effects would contribute to a slightly higher modelled AOD – as an example, it is
44 known that pyroconvective phenomena generated by wildfires can kick non-neglectable
45 quantities of dust into the atmosphere, thus further increasing the AOD.

46 Additionally, as mentioned in the main manuscript, herein is a more detailed discussion
47 of the emissions and their impacts over the region of Canada. AOD differences between FIRE and
48 noFIRE are greatest in central-western and central regions, which is an expected consequence of
49 the fact that wildfire emissions are localized in that area (Fig. 1). Despite this, a clear longitudinal
50 gradient is obvious in the aerosol impact plots, wherein the westernmost regions of Canada are
51 the least affected by the effects of wildfire emissions (Fig. 3). The atmospheric temperature
52 anomaly shows a consistent west-east (W-E) gradient, with western and central-western regions
53 exhibiting the least cooling and central, central-eastern and eastern regions exhibiting the most
54 cooling. The W-E temperature gradient cannot fully be explained solely by direct AOD effects,
55 however in central-eastern and eastern regions accentuated cooling is matched by relatively low
56 AOD loadings but correlates instead with increases in cloud cover, meaning that the W-E cooling
57 gradient over Canada is best explained by a dual mechanism of direct AOD effects and cloud
58 cover enhancements from indirect AOD effects.

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 60 Fig. 3-S: Global differences (FIRE – noFIRE) averaged across May-September for atmospheric
 61 temperature at different pressure levels: (a) 1000 hPa, (b) 850 hPa, (c) 500 hPa, (d) 200 hPa.

62 Global atmospheric temperature changes at four different pressure heights are also shown
 63 (Fig. 3-S). A slight heating anomaly is found at the 200hPa level (Fig. 3-S(d)). This occurs due to a
 64 well-known atmospheric heating mechanism at higher altitudes due to BC-containing wildfire
 65 smoke injection.

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 67 Fig. 4-S: Month-by-month spatial cross-correlation between the changes (FIRE – noFIRE) in a)
 68 surface atmospheric temperature and black carbon AOD, b) surface atmospheric temperature and
 69 organic carbon AOD.

70 Finally, plots of spatial cross-correlation between the BC AOD and OC AOD differences
 71 and surface atmospheric temperature differences are shown (Fig. 4-S). The temporal evolution of

72 these correlation plots is very similar to that of the AOD correlations, since these aerosol species
73 produce similar effects to the surface temperature.